

Zebra_K⁺ : High-throughput analysis of acoustic startle response plasticity in zebrafish embryos and larvae in neurotoxicity testing

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ABSTRACT

The acoustic startle response (ASR) is a conserved sensorimotor reflex widely used to investigate neural plasticity, sensorimotor gating, and neurotoxicity. While zebrafish is an established vertebrate model for ASR analysis, most existing platforms were originally optimized for 6 dpf larvae, which constrains applications requiring reliable assessment of earlier developmental stages. Here, we introduce Zebra_K⁺, a modular extension of the previously developed Zebra_K platform, designed for high-throughput kinematic analysis of ASR in zebrafish embryos (5 days post-fertilization, dpf) and early larvae (6–7 dpf). The system enables simultaneous quantification of ASR kinematics, sensitivity, short-term habituation, and prepulse inhibition (PPI) in up to 25 individuals. Using the NMDA receptor antagonist ketamine, the dopamine receptor agonist apomorphine, and the D₂ receptor antagonist haloperidol, we validated the platform's ability to detect pharmacologically induced and developmentally specific alterations in startle plasticity. Ketamine reduced habituation and PPI at all developmental stages, whereas apomorphine selectively impaired PPI, an effect that was reversed by haloperidol only at 7 dpf. These results demonstrate the neurodevelopmental progression of glutamatergic and dopaminergic modulation of sensorimotor gating and establish Zebra_K⁺ as a modular technological platform that supports the development of New Approach Methods (NAMs) for neurotoxicological screening and developmental neuropsychology.

1. Introduction

The startle response is a rapid, involuntary motor reflex triggered by sudden, intense sensory input that serves as a defense mechanism conserved in all vertebrates. In mammals, the acoustic startle response (ASR) is mediated by a brainstem circuit in which auditory input activates the caudal pontine reticular nucleus (PnC), which in turn recruits motor neurons to produce the characteristic muscular contraction (Gómez-Nieto et al., 2014; Lauer et al., 2017). Alterations in ASR reactivity are observed across a range of neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders (Chen and Toth, 2001; O'Leary et al., 2017; Siegelaaar et al., 2006).

ASR plasticity is commonly assessed using habituation and prepulse inhibition (PPI), two processes central to sensorimotor gating, the brain's ability to filter out irrelevant sensory information. Habituation is a non-associative form of learning in which repeated, non-threatening

stimuli elicit progressively smaller responses (Koch, 1999; López-Schier, 2019). PPI occurs when a weak, non-startling prepulse presented shortly before a startling pulse attenuates the startle response (Swerdlow and Geyer, 1998). Dysregulation of habituation and PPI is a hallmark of several central nervous system disorders, including schizophrenia and obsessive-compulsive disorder, and similar alterations have been observed following exposure to neurotoxic compounds affecting dopaminergic or glutamatergic signaling (Brun et al., 2021; Koch et al., 1992; Panlilio et al., 2020). Therefore, these measures serve as sensitive behavioral endophenotypes for both translational neuroscience and neurotoxicological research (Hoening et al., 2005; Sato, 2020).

Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) is an established vertebrate model for neurobehavioral research due to their genetic tractability and conserved neural circuitry and neurotransmitter systems (Babin et al., 2014). The ASR in zebrafish is mediated by the Mauthner-cell circuit, where a single Mauthner action potential triggers a rapid C-bend escape response

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(Medan and Preuss, 2014), lending itself to high-throughput kinematic analysis. Whereas this system is anatomically simpler than the distributed PnC network that mediates the mammalian startle, it shares key functional properties, including rapid sensorimotor transformation, monosynaptic reticulospinal output, and modulation by conserved neurotransmitter pathways, supporting the translational relevance of ASR plasticity among vertebrates. Although many classical studies of ASR plasticity have historically focused on 6 dpf larvae because early experimental platforms were optimized for that stage, several investigations have demonstrated that 5 dpf embryos can already exhibit reliable ASR responsiveness, habituation, and PPI (Bhandiwad et al., 2013; Leuthold et al., 2025; McAtee and Abdelmoneim, 2024; Zeddies and Fay, 2005). These systems have been instrumental for dissecting neural circuits and modeling psychiatric endophenotypes (Banono et al., 2020; Campbell et al., 2023; Jain et al., 2018; Marsden et al., 2018). In recent years, eleuthero-embryonic stages such as 5 dpf have also gained increasing attention in environmental neurotoxicology, partly due to broader implementation of New Approach Methods (NAMs) (De Castelbajac et al., 2023; Ramhøj et al., 2024; Tal et al., 2024), which encourage the use of non-feeding developmental stages where feasible. In this context, extending behavioral platforms to reliably assess neuroplasticity and sensorimotor gating at 5 dpf is increasingly relevant and complements the more established assays performed at 6 dpf.

While eleuthero-embryonic stages are increasingly incorporated into environmental neurotoxicology, the utility of early-stage ASR assays extends well beyond regulatory-driven contexts. High-resolution analysis of sensorimotor responses at 5 dpf provides an opportunity to address a wide range of questions in developmental neurobiology, neurobehavioral sciences, neuropharmacology, and mechanistic neurotoxicology. Establishing reliable methods to quantify ASR kinematics, habituation, and PPI at this stage therefore strengthens both NAM-oriented applications and fundamental research into circuit maturation and early behavioral plasticity.

We recently developed Zebra_K, an automated kinematic platform to assess ASR sensitivity, habituation, and PPI in adult zebrafish (Stevanović et al., 2025). Here we introduce Zebra_K*, a modular add-on designed for embryos (5 dpf) and early larvae (6–7 dpf) that extends Zebra_K's capabilities to high-throughput measurement of ASR kinematics, sensitivity, short-term habituation, and PPI in up to 25 individuals simultaneously. We validated Zebra_K* pharmacologically using the NMDA receptor antagonist ketamine, the dopamine receptor agonist apomorphine, and the D₂ antagonist haloperidol, demonstrating the platform's sensitivity to concentration-dependent and developmentally specific modulation of sensorimotor gating. Zebra_K* therefore provides a flexible, scalable tool for developmental neurobehavioral studies and neurotoxicological screening.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animals and housing

Adult wild-type short-fin (SF) zebrafish (standard length: 2.0–3.0 cm) were sourced from Exopet (Madrid, Spain). SF zebrafish constitute a genetically heterogeneous, outbred wild-type stock rather than an inbred laboratory strain (e.g., AB, Tübingen, TL). This choice follows established recommendations in zebrafish behavioral neuroscience, as outbred stocks avoid strain-specific idiosyncrasies associated with inbreeding-related genetic drift and better preserve behavioral phenotypes representative of natural populations (Sison and Gerlai, 2011). Fish were housed in the CID-CSIC facility within a recirculating aquaculture system from Aquaneering Inc. (San Diego, United States).

Embryos were generated via natural spawning, with a mating ratio of three females to two males per tank. Following collection, fertilized embryos were placed into 6-well plates, with 20 embryos in 10 mL of fish water per well. The fish water consisted of MilliQ water supplemented with 90 mg/L of Instant Ocean (Aquarium Systems, Sarrebourg,

France) and 0.58 mM CaSO₄·2 H₂O, with a pH of 6.5–7.0 and conductivity ranging from 750 to 900 µS/cm. Embryos were maintained at a constant temperature of 28 °C ± 1 °C in a POL-EKO APARATURA Climatic chamber (KK350, Wodzislaw Slaski, Poland) under a 12-hour light/12-hour dark cycle (08:00–20:00 h). Fish water was refreshed daily from 24 h post-collection until the behavioral assays were performed.

Following established developmental staging criteria (Kimmel et al., 1995) and regulatory definitions (Embry et al., 2010; Strähle et al., 2012; OECD GD 49), 5 dpf zebrafish are considered eleuthero-embryos, as they have hatched but still rely on endogenous yolk stores. For simplicity, we use the term “embryo” throughout the manuscript to refer to this stage, whereas 6–7 dpf individuals are classified as early larvae due to the onset of exogenous feeding and further maturation of sensorimotor circuits.

During the 5–7 days post-fertilization (dpf) window, zebrafish larvae are in an endoexotrophic period, consuming both residual yolk and external food (Poupard et al., 2000). To mitigate variability from external feeding, larvae were not provided food throughout the experiments. All animal protocols received approval from the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) at the CID-CSIC and were authorized by the local government under agreement No 11336.

2.2. Zebra_K⁺: hardware description

The Zebra_K⁺ observation chamber (Fig. 1A) was designed and built at the Institut of Robòtica i Informàtica Industrial (CSIC-UPC) for imaging zebrafish embryos and early larvae. It was conceived as an add-on module (Fig. 1B) that can be mounted on the Zebra_K observation chamber (Stevanović et al., 2025) using fixed guides, with the chamber's inner end wall serving as a mechanical stop. When switching between the adult module and the embryo module, the camera focus must be readjusted to compensate for the difference in module height. This adjustment is quickly and easily performed by monitoring the live camera feed in real time.

The embryos add-on module is equipped with its own amplifier, speaker, and light regulator (Fig. 1C). These components interface with the Zebra_K observation chamber through two connectors, labeled “DAC IN” and “12 V” in Fig. 1B-C. A schematic of the main components and connections of the new add-on module is provided in Fig. 1D. The setup incorporates a compact PETG grid with 25 square experimental arenas (10 × 10 mm, 3 mm height), each containing a single zebrafish embryo/larva in 0.15 mL of fish water. As shown in Fig. 1C-D, the grid rests on a translucent surface illuminated from below by 16 infrared LEDs (OSRAM SFH 4556) evenly distributed at the base. A 66 mm diameter, 4 Ω, 5 W speaker (Amazon, ASIN: B097BHFD5X) is positioned 98 mm below the grid, beneath the illumination system. The speaker generates airborne acoustic pulses that propagate through the chamber and reach the water surface of each arena. Sound pressure level (SPL) of the stimuli was measured at the arena level using a PCE-322A sonometer (PCE Instruments, Meschede, Germany), ensuring consistent stimulus amplitude between trials.

Because each arena contains only 150–250 µL of water, *in situ* acoustic waveform characterization with an underwater hydrophone is technically unfeasible. Instead, reproducibility of stimulus transmission was verified through SPL measurements together with high-speed video recordings. High-speed recordings revealed a slight, reproducible displacement of the grid immediately after pulse emission. This frame was used as a practical marker of stimulus onset (time 0) for latency measurements. The onset of the short-latency C-bend consistently occurred 4–8 ms after this frame, matching the latency range previously reported for Mauthner-cell-mediated escape responses in zebrafish larvae (Burgess and Granato, 2007).

Behavioral responses to the airborne acoustic pulses were recorded with the high-speed camera integrated in the Zebra_K⁺ observation chamber (Photron Fastcam Mini UX100, equipped with a 28 mm Sigma

Fig. 1. Zebra_K⁺ observation chamber (A) Zebra_K⁺ observation chamber, with the module for adults on the bottom of the chamber and the new embryo add-on module on the top. (B-C) The embryo add-on module (B) is equipped with its own amplifier, speaker, and light regulator (C). (D) Diagram of the platform Zebra_K⁺, identifying the main components and connections of the observation chamber with the embryo add-on module.

F1.4 DG HSM Art lens). This camera acquires 1024×1024 pixel images at 1000 frames per second. The acquisition is triggered by a microprocessor (Arm Cortex-M4-based STM32F4), which also controls stimulus delivery, thereby ensuring precise synchronization between acoustic stimulation and video capture.

2.3. Zebra_K⁺: software description

Zebra_K⁺ uses the same control software developed for Zebra_K (Stevanović et al., 2025). This software allows the user to design specific sequences of acoustic stimuli, manage experiment timing, and synchronize hardware operations, including video acquisition and download. With the integration of the embryo add-on module, the software was updated to enable users to select whether the programmed stimulus sequence is delivered through the adult fish platform or the embryo module. The user interface of the control software is MATLAB-based, and the communication with the microcontroller is through a USB-UART cable. The microcontroller is programmed to implement the sequence with microsecond precision.

Image analysis is performed using the Zebrafish Acoustic Startle Response kinematic analysis software (Stevanović et al., 2025), adapted

here for embryos and larvae. This software is Python-based and uses Deeplabcut libraries to perform larva skeleton tracking. Finally, it processes the data to extract the corresponding kinematics parameters for each individual. The adaptation to larvae system consists of implementing a new neural network specifically trained on larval data. This network was labeled using four body points per larva (Fig. 2A). In addition, several new features were added to enhance data visualization and interpretation, including improved graphing, video output, and data filtering capabilities. These improvements were essential, as each video now contains data from 25 embryos/larvae processed simultaneously (Fig. 2B).

2.4. Experimental procedure

All experiments with the Zebra_K⁺ platform were carried out in a dedicated behavioral room maintained at 27–28 °C, between 10:00–17:00 h. Zebrafish embryos at 5 dpf and early larvae at 6–7 dpf were transferred to the behavioral room one hour prior to testing for acclimation.

Prior to each trial, larvae were screened, and only individuals without morphological malformations (normal body axis, inflated swim

A

B

Fig. 2. Zebra K⁺ kinematic analysis software. (A) Grid containing 25 zebrafish embryos at 5 days post-fertilization, with four body points (colored dots) automatically detected by the neural network on each embryo. (B) Three representative traces of the acoustic startle response (ASR) for all embryos or early larvae in the grid, as generated by the analysis software.

bladder, and absence of edema) were selected for behavioral assessment. Selected larvae were transferred from 6-well plates into the 3D-printed grid of the Zebra K⁺ device using wide-bore plastic pipettes to minimize handling stress. For pretreatment periods (e.g., haloperidol exposure), larvae were placed into each well in 150 μ L of medium for 20 min. Immediately before behavioral testing, an additional 100 μ L of the corresponding solution was added to each well, bringing the final volume to 250 μ L, in which all behavioral assays were conducted. Larvae remained in the grid throughout the entire behavioral sequence without further manipulation.

The kinematic features of the ASR were determined using a startle-inducing stimulus (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa), which consistently evoked responses in 60–90 % of the embryos and early larvae

tested (Burgess and Granato, 2007; Stevanović et al., 2025). This high-response stimulus was selected because clear, well-resolved startle events are required for reliable extraction of kinematic parameters.

The assessment of ASR sensitivity and short-habituation followed a protocol adapted from Wolman et al. (2011). The stimulus parameters were initially optimized based on response frequencies obtained in 5 dpf embryos, and the same conditions were subsequently applied to 6–7 dpf larvae to allow for direct developmental comparisons. The procedure began with a sensitivity phase consisting of five mild stimuli (1000 Hz, 100 μ s, 85.9 dB re 20 μ Pa), which typically elicited 15–30 % of responses, delivered at 120-s interstimulus interval (ISI). After a 60-s rest period, five startle-inducing stimuli (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa) were presented during the prehabituation phase, with an ISI of 120 s.

Following another 60-s rest, habituation was evaluated by administering fifteen identical startle stimuli with a shortened ISI of 2 s. The degree of habituation was quantified by comparing mean response level across the early (stimuli 1–5), middle (stimuli 6–10), and late (stimuli 11–15) portions of this sequence with the mean obtained during the prehabilitation phase (Wolman et al., 2011).

For each experimental condition, startle responsiveness was quantified at the group level. For every stimulus—whether part of the sensitivity, prehabilitation, habituation, prepulse, pulse, or prepulse-pulse phases—each larva was classified as a responder (1) or non-responder (0). The percentage of responses for a given stimulus was calculated as the proportion of larvae exhibiting an ASR to that specific stimulus. Consequently, each plate yields five percentage values for the sensitivity phase, five for the prehabilitation phase, fifteen for the habituation phase (organized into blocks of five stimuli), and stimulus-specific percentages for all PPI phases, regardless of the number of larvae per group. Thus, percentages represent stimulus-specific, group-level response probabilities rather than per-individual averages. All raw responder classifications, per-stimulus percentages, and the exact number of larvae included or excluded in each group are provided in [Supplementary Datasets 1–4](#).

PPI was determined using a three-step paradigm adapted from Burgess and Granato (2007) and Stevanović et al. (2025). In the prepulse step, five weak stimuli (1000 Hz, 20 μ s, 74.8 dB re 20 μ Pa), which typically induced 0–10 % of responses, were delivered at 120-s ISI. After a 60-s pause, five startle-inducing stimuli (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa) were presented in the pulse step, also with a 120-s ISI. Finally, following another 60-s rest, prepulse-pulse combinations were administered in the PPI step, with intervals between the two stimuli ranging from 50 to 500 ms, and 120-s ISI between successive pairs. The percentage of PPI was calculated as:

$$\text{PPI (\%)} = 100 \times (\% \text{Response_Pulse} - \% \text{Response_Prepulse+Pulse}) / \% \text{Response_Pulse}$$

2.5. Pharmacological modulation of ASR

To evaluate the pharmacological modulation of ASR, we used ketamine as an NMDA receptor antagonist, apomorphine as a dopamine receptor agonist, and haloperidol as a D₂ receptor antagonist, following established approaches (Burgess and Granato, 2007; Wolman et al., 2011). The compounds tested were ketamine hydrochloride (K27653; Purity \geq 99 %, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, USA), (R)-apomorphine hydrochloride hemihydrate (FA17955, Biosynth s.r.o., Bratislava, Slovakia), and haloperidol (H1512; Purity \geq 98 %, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, USA). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO; D8418, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, USA) was used as solvent where required. All solutions were freshly prepared on the day of the experiment. Haloperidol was dissolved in 100 % DMSO to prepare a primary stock, from which a 70 μ M intermediate stock (10 % DMSO) was generated. This intermediate stock was diluted to obtain the working solutions used for the 20-minute pretreatment (0.5 μ M haloperidol, 0.1 % DMSO) and for the co-exposure mixture (0.5 μ M haloperidol + 35 μ M apomorphine, 0.1 % DMSO). The haloperidol concentration (0.5 μ M) was selected based on Burgess and Granato (2007). That study demonstrated that 0.1–1.0 μ M haloperidol effectively blocks D₂ receptor activation during apomorphine exposure while not altering PPI when administered alone. Accordingly, haloperidol was not tested as an independent treatment, in order to avoid redundant animal use in line with the 3Rs and institutional ethical guidelines. Apomorphine was dissolved in fish water to prepare a 10 mM stock, which was diluted to produce the working solutions for apomorphine exposure (35 μ M, 0.1 % DMSO) and for the apomorphine+haloperidol mixture. Ketamine was dissolved directly in fish water and diluted to 50 μ M for habituation

experiments and 500 μ M for PPI experiments. When necessary, additional DMSO was added to ensure that all experimental conditions, including vehicle controls, contained a final concentration of 0.1 % DMSO.

Larvae were exposed individually, with one larva per well in the 3D-printed Zebra K* grid; therefore, each larva constituted one biological replicate. At the beginning of each assay, larvae were placed in 150 μ L of the corresponding solution. After the pretreatment phase (for haloperidol assays), 100 μ L of the appropriate working solution were added to reach a final exposure volume of 250 μ L, in which all behavioral tests were conducted under continuous exposure. Control and treatment groups were always run in parallel during the same experimental session, and a daily 0.1 % DMSO vehicle-control group was included. Only morphologically normal larvae (normal axis, inflated swim bladder, no edema) were used for analysis.

For all assessments, subjects were exposed to the compound and allowed to acclimate for 30 min before testing, which was then conducted under continuous exposure. In experiments involving haloperidol, a 20-minute pretreatment was followed by co-exposure with apomorphine, as described above. Each larva was tested individually (one larva per well), and treatment groups were initially assembled with approximately 25 larvae per developmental stage. Final sample sizes varied slightly between experiments due to the exclusion of larvae with morphological abnormalities and the predefined criterion for behavioral exclusion (<20 % responses during the prehabilitation phase). The exact number of larvae analyzed in each experiment is reported in the figure legends and fully documented in [Supplementary Datasets 1–4](#).

Following range-finding tests, the selected concentrations for the habituation experiments were 50 and 500 μ M ketamine and 35 μ M apomorphine. These values were chosen starting from effective doses previously reported for 5 dpf embryos and adults (ketamine: 100–500 μ M in 5 dpf embryos, (Wolman et al., 2011); 50 μ M in adults, (Stevanović et al., 2025)). For PPI experiments, 500 μ M ketamine was selected because lower concentrations, including 50 μ M, do not consistently disrupt PPI in early larvae, whereas concentrations between 100–3000 μ M are effective in 6 dpf larvae (Burgess and Granato, 2007). The chosen doses of apomorphine (35 μ M) and haloperidol (0.5 μ M) were likewise based on previously reported effective ranges for PPI modulation in larvae (apomorphine: 5–20 μ g/mL \approx 15–60 μ M; haloperidol: 0.1–1 μ M, (Burgess and Granato, 2007)).

2.6. Robustness analysis

To assess the robustness of the automated behavioral platform, we evaluated whether each behavioral parameter remained stable across independent experimental batches (groups and/or experiments). The analysis included parameters from the kinematic, habituation, and prepulse inhibition (PPI) domains in 5 dpf embryos. Because data distributions did not meet the criteria for normality (Shapiro–Wilk test, $p < 0.05$), nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis (KW) tests were used to compare results obtained from independent experiments.

For kinematic variables (latency, maximal angular velocity, bending angle, and bending duration), analyses were performed at the individual fish level using all available reactions. In contrast, habituation and PPI parameters were evaluated at the group level, since they were defined as the percentage of responding animals (responders vs. non-responders) within each group and/or experiment.

The corresponding Asymptotic Significance (p) values were used to determine inter-experimental differences, with $p < 0.05$ considered indicative of potential batch effects. This approach quantifies the robustness of the platform—its ability to produce consistent measurements across independent sessions or experimental conditions

2.7. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS v29 (Statistical

Package 2010, Chicago, IL, USA), and data visualizations were generated in GraphPad Prism 9 for Windows (GraphPad software Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA).

The normality of each dataset was evaluated using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Variables that violated normality assumptions ($p < 0.05$) were analyzed using non-parametric tests: Kruskal–Wallis tests were applied when comparing three or more groups, followed by Mann–Whitney U tests for pairwise comparisons when required. For datasets that satisfied normality assumptions, comparisons among groups were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett’s and/or Tukey’s post hoc test. All analyses were two-tailed, and statistical significance was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. Parametric data are presented as the mean \pm standard error (SEM), while non-parametric data are shown as the median and interquartile range (IQR).

3. Results

3.1. Kinematic parameters of the ASR in zebrafish embryos and early larvae

Kinematic analysis of the acoustic startle responses (ASR) elicited by a startle-inducing auditory stimulus (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa) was performed in zebrafish at 5 dpf ($n = 194$ reactions), 6 dpf ($n = 164$ reactions), and 7 dpf ($n = 137$ reactions). Fig. 3 summarizes the main kinematic parameters of the short-latency C-bend (SLC) determined by Zebra-K⁺ for each developmental stage, including latency, average angular velocity, as well as C-bend angle and duration. Individual data points for each parameter and developmental stage are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 1](#).

The latency of the C-bend (Fig. 3A,C) increased slightly but significantly with age [$H(2, N = 495) = 24.1, p = 5.94 \times 10^{-6}$], being higher

Fig. 3. Kinematic values of acoustic startle responses (ASR) in 5 dpf (194 reactions) and 6 dpf (164 reactions) and 7 dpf (137 reactions) zebrafish. Histograms of latency (A) and C-bend angle (B), and the main kinematic values of these responses (C). IQR: interquartile range. Acoustic stimulus: 1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa. Latency: time where the embryo or larva reaction is detected after the beginning of the acoustic stimulus; C-bend duration: duration (ms) of the first movement sinusoid (C-bend); C-bend angle: difference between the maximal body curvature during the C-bend and the initial body curvature at the latency time.

at 7 dpf compared to 5 and 6 dpf. Approximately 80 % of responses at 5 dpf occurred within 4–7 ms, whereas at 6–7 dpf, most latencies ranged from 4 to 8 ms. No significant differences were observed among developmental stages for the average angular velocity [$H(2, N = 495) = 0.44, p = 0.801$], maximal angular velocity [$H(2, N = 495) = 3.74, p = 0.154$], C-bend angle [$H(2, N = 495) = 5.96, p = 0.051$], and C-bend duration [$H(2, N = 495) = 4.92, p = 0.086$]. Moreover, across the five kinematic variables (latency, average angular velocity, maximal angular velocity, C-bend angle, and C-bend duration) and the three developmental stages (5–7 dpf) analyzed, responses from different fish and experimental runs did not differ significantly in 29 of 30 comparisons ($p > 0.05$, Kruskal–Wallis and Mann–Whitney tests), indicating the

reliability and robustness of the Zebra_K* platform for quantifying kinematic parameters.

3.2. Short-term habituation of ASR: effect of developmental stage

To assess short-term habituation of the ASR, we adapted and optimized a three-phase protocol originally developed by [Stevanović et al. \(2025\)](#) for adult zebrafish. Each phase of the habituation protocol consisted of a defined series of acoustic stimuli of either moderate or high intensity, separated by specific interstimulus intervals ([Santistevan et al., 2022](#); [Wolman et al., 2011](#)). During the sensitivity phase, a moderate stimulus (1000 Hz, 100 μ s, 85.9 dB re 20 μ Pa) was used to

Fig. 4. Short-term habituation to acoustic stimuli in zebrafish embryos (5 dpf) and larvae (6–7 dpf). (A) ASR frequencies across the sensitivity, prehabitation, and habituation phases recorded using the Zebra_K* protocol. The sensitivity stimulus was a moderate acoustic pulse (1000 Hz, 100 μ s, 85.9 dB re 20 μ Pa), whereas the prehabitation and habituation phases used a startle-inducing stimulus (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa). (B) ASR frequencies summarized for the sensitivity, prehabitation, early habituation (stimuli 1–5), middle habituation (stimuli 6–10), and late habituation (stimuli 11–15) phases. Sample sizes were 60 embryos (5 dpf), 54 larvae (6 dpf), and 61 larvae (7 dpf), yielding 30, 30, and 35 ASR-percentage values per age and phase, respectively. Data are presented as boxplots where the box indicates the 25th and 75th percentiles, the thin line within the box marks the median, and the whiskers the maximum and minimum values, showing all data. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$; Kruskal Wallis test with Bonferroni correction. All individual %ASR values are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 2](#).

determine baseline responsiveness, typically eliciting startle reactions in approximately 20–40 % of the individuals. A stronger acoustic pulse (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa), which evoked startle responses in about 70–90 % of the population, was then applied in the prehabitation and habituation phases to evaluate short-term plasticity of the startle reflex in 5–7 dpf zebrafish (Fig. 4A). Five stimuli were delivered at 120-s intervals during the sensitivity and prehabitation phases, followed by a series of fifteen startle-inducing stimuli delivered every 2 s during the habituation phase. This design allowed us to characterize both the initial responsiveness to acoustic input and the progressive decline in startle probability across repeated stimulation. Individual response frequencies and calculated percentage habituation values for each developmental stage are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 2](#).

As shown in Fig. 4B, during the sensitivity phase, the frequency of startle responses differed markedly among developmental stages [$H(2, N = 95) = 27.17, p < 0.0001$]. The proportion of embryos responding at 5 dpf (median: 37.5 %) was significantly higher than at 6 dpf (median: 14.3 %, $p = 0.006$) and 7 dpf (median: 0 %, $p < 0.0001$). These results indicate a progressive reduction in startle sensitivity with age, suggesting that older larvae require stronger stimuli to elicit comparable motor reactions.

In the prehabitation phase, consisting of five startle-inducing stimuli of higher intensity delivered at 120-s intervals, developmental differences persisted [$H(2, N = 95) = 9.27, p = 0.009$]. The 5 dpf embryos exhibited the highest responsiveness (median: 91.7 %), which was significantly greater than in 6 dpf larvae (median: 83.3 %; $p = 0.012$). Overall, responsiveness to strong acoustic pulses remained high across all ages, but a subtle downward trend was evident as development advanced.

Analysis of short-term habituation, quantified as the progressive decline in response probability through the early (stimuli 1–5), middle (stimuli 6–10), and late (stimuli 11–15) stimulus blocks, revealed no significant differences among developmental stages. Despite the age-related decrease in baseline sensitivity, all groups exhibited a comparable ability to habituate to repeated acoustic stimulation.

Moreover, across the five habituation-related variables (sensitivity, prehabitation, and early, middle, and late habituation) and the three developmental stages (5–7 dpf) analyzed, responses from different groups of fish and independent experimental runs did not differ significantly in 28 of 30 comparisons ($p > 0.05$, Kruskal–Wallis and Mann–Whitney tests), further demonstrating the reliability and robustness of the ZebraK⁺ platform for quantifying startle sensitivity and short-term habituation.

3.3. Prepulse inhibition of ASR: effect of developmental stage

The suitability of the ZebraK⁺ platform to assess prepulse inhibition (PPI) in zebrafish embryos and early larvae was evaluated using a protocol adapted from [Stevanović et al. \(2025\)](#). A weak acoustic stimulus (1000 Hz, 20 μ s, 74.8 dB re 20 μ Pa), which typically elicited 0–10 % startle responses, was selected as the prepulse. The pulse consisted of the same startle-inducing stimulus used in the prehabitation phase of the habituation protocol (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa). The PPI sequence included five prepulse-alone trials (interstimulus interval, ISI = 120 s), followed by five pulse-alone trials (ISI = 120 s), and five combined prepulse–pulse sequences (ISI between sequences = 120 s), with prepulse–pulse intervals of 50 and 500 ms. Individual response frequencies and calculated PPI percentage values for each developmental stage are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 3](#).

Fig. 5 summarizes the ASR frequencies for 5–7 dpf zebrafish across the four phases of the optimized PPI protocol. Median ASR frequency during the prepulse phase was 0 % for all developmental stages. In response to the pulse-alone condition, startle responsiveness was high at all ages: 91.7 % (IQR: 83.3–100 %) for 5 dpf embryos, 88.9 % (IQR: 77.8–100 %) for 6 dpf larvae, and 91.7 % (IQR: 75.0–100 %) for 7 dpf larvae.

Presentation of a prepulse 50 ms before the pulse caused a marked reduction in startle responsiveness at all stages, with median ASR frequencies of 25.0 % (IQR: 16.7–33.3 %) for 5 dpf, 18.2 % (IQR: 8.3–33.3 %) for 6 dpf, and 29.2 % (IQR: 16.7–40.0 %) for 7 dpf. When the prepulse preceded the pulse by 500 ms, ASR frequency also decreased, though to a lesser extent: 41.7 % (IQR: 25.0–60.4 %) for 5 dpf, 50.0 % (IQR: 33.3–63.6 %) for 6 dpf, and 35.4 % (IQR: 25.0–57.5 %) for 7 dpf. These reductions in responsiveness were statistically significant for all ages [5 dpf: $H(2, N = 90) = 63.2, p < 0.0001$; 6 dpf: $H(2, N = 105) = 68.7, p < 0.0001$; 7 dpf: $H(2, N = 120) = 68.8, p < 0.0001$].

No significant differences in PPI magnitude were observed within developmental stages. The median percentage of inhibition for 5, 6, and 7 dpf zebrafish was 72.5 % (IQR: 63.0–81.8 %), 75.4 % (IQR: 59.2–91.0 %), and 68.2 % (IQR: 48.6–78.3 %) at the 50 ms interval, and 54.9 % (IQR: 30.0–72.6 %), 38.6 % (IQR: 32.0–64.9 %), and 56.1 % (IQR: 34.4–73.3 %) at the 500 ms interval. Within each developmental stage, PPI responses were consistent across zebrafish groups and experiments in 22 out of 24 comparisons.

Fig. 5. Prepulse inhibition (PPI) of the acoustic startle response (ASR) in zebrafish embryos (5 dpf) and early larvae (6–7 dpf). ASR frequencies are shown for the prepulse phase, the pulse-alone phase, and the combined prepulse–pulse trials. The prepulse consisted of a weak acoustic stimulus (1000 Hz, 20 μ s, 74.8 dB re 20 μ Pa), whereas the pulse was a startle-inducing stimulus (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa). Sample sizes of 66 embryos (5 dpf), 73 larvae (6 dpf), and 76 larvae (7 dpf) were used, yielding 30, 35, and 40 ASR-percentage values per age and phase, respectively. Data are presented as boxplots in which the box indicates the 25th and 75th percentiles, the line marks the median, and the whiskers represent the minimum and maximum values, showing all data. Kruskal–Wallis test with Bonferroni correction: ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$. All individual ASR-percentage values are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 3](#).

3.4. Pharmacological modulation of ASR sensitivity and short-term habituation

3.4.1. Glutamatergic modulation

NMDA-type glutamate receptor (NMDAR) antagonists have been shown to reduce ASR habituation in several animal models, including mice and zebrafish larvae (Bickel et al., 2007; Wolman et al., 2011). To validate the capacity of Zebra_K⁺ to detect altered short-term habituation, we examined the effects of the NMDAR antagonist ketamine in zebrafish embryos and early larvae. Individual response frequencies and calculated percentage habituation values for each developmental stage are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 4](#).

At 5 dpf, treatment significantly affected habituation across all phases [$H(2, N = 45) = 22.50, p < 0.0001$], middle [$H(2) = 30.84, p < 0.0001$], and late [$H(2) = 25.03, p < 0.0001$]. As shown in [Fig. 6](#), embryos exposed to 500 μM ketamine showed a marked reduction in the three phases of habituation, whereas those exposed to 50 μM ketamine did not show any effect on habituation. No significant effects were observed for sensitivity or prehabituation at this developmental stage.

At 6 dpf, exposure to 500 μM ketamine significantly increased responsiveness during the prehabituation phase [$H(2, N = 45) = 9.86, p = 0.007$] and reduced early [$H(2) = 15.22, p = 0.0005$], middle [$H(2) = 33.04, p < 0.0001$], and late [$H(2) = 34.05, p < 0.0001$] habituation compared with controls ([Fig. 6](#)). Larvae exposed to both ketamine concentrations also showed increased sensitivity [$H(2) = 18.30, p = 0.0001$].

Similarly, at 7 dpf, exposure to 500 μM ketamine led to a significant increase in responsiveness during the prehabituation step [$H(2, N = 45) = 9.91, p = 0.007$], along with decreased early [$H(2) = 16.81, p = 0.0002$], middle [$H(2) = 12.51, p = 0.002$], and late [$H(2) = 12.77, p = 0.002$] habituation compared with controls ([Fig. 6](#)). These larvae also exhibited increased sensitivity [$H(2) = 26.48, p < 0.0001$].

3.4.2. Dopaminergic modulation

To further validate the ability of Zebra_K⁺, we assessed whether short-term exposure to apomorphine, a non-selective dopamine receptor agonist, alters ASR sensitivity and short-term habituation across developmental stages in zebrafish embryos (5dpf) and larvae (6–7 dpf). Individual response frequencies and calculated PPI percentage values for each developmental stage are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 5](#).

As shown in [Supplementary Figure 1](#), zebrafish exposed to 35 μM apomorphine exhibited a strong and significant decrease in ASR sensitivity across all developmental stages analyzed compared with controls [5 dpf: $U(N_{\text{control}} = 15, N_{\text{apomorphine}} = 15) = 12.5, z = -4.299, p < 0.0001$; 6 dpf: $U = 35.0, z = -3.253, p = 0.0008$; 7 dpf: $U = 48.0, z = -3.191, p = 0.006$].

Regarding habituation, significant treatment effects were observed only in 5 dpf embryos ([Supplementary Figure 1](#)), which displayed reduced middle [$U(N_{\text{control}} = 15, N_{\text{apomorphine}} = 15) = 41.5, z = -3.048, p = 0.002$] and late [$U = 38.0, z = -3.308, p = 0.001$] habituation relative to controls. Although the effect on early habituation was not statistically significant, it showed a similar decreasing trend [$U = 65.0, z = -1.977, p = 0.05$].

During the prehabituation step, no significant treatment effects were observed on responsiveness to the startle-inducing stimulus at any developmental stage.

Our results show that apomorphine (35 μM) significantly reduces sensitivity to a weak startle-inducing stimulus in zebrafish embryos and larvae (5–7 dpf), while leaving responses to the stronger prehabituation stimulus unaffected. This selective effect indicates that dopaminergic activation dampens responsiveness to lower-intensity stimuli without broadly impairing startle reactions.

3.5. Pharmacological modulation of sensorimotor gating

3.5.1. Glutamatergic modulation

In humans as well as in different animal models, NMDA receptor antagonists such as ketamine or MK-801 result in PPI impairment (Braff et al., 2001; Canal et al., 2001; Gómez-Nieto et al., 2020; Sandner et al., 2002). A similar effect has been reported in zebrafish larvae (Banono and Esguerra, 2020; Burgess and Granato, 2007) and adults (Stevanović et al., 2025). Therefore, we assessed whether a 30-min exposure to 50 μM ketamine alters PPI across developmental stages in zebrafish embryos (5 dpf) and larvae (6–7 dpf). Individual response frequencies and calculated percentage PPI values for each developmental stage are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 6](#).

As shown in [Fig. 7A](#), zebrafish exposed to 50 μM ketamine exhibited a strong and significant decrease in PPI at all developmental stages compared with controls, using prepulse–pulse intervals of 50 ms [5 dpf: $t(28) = 4.66, p < 0.0001$; 6 dpf: $t(28) = 3.71, p = 0.0009$; 7 dpf: $t(28) = 3.89, p = 0.0006$] and 500 ms [5 dpf: $U(N_{\text{control}} = 15, N_{\text{ketamine}} = 15) = 7.00, z = -4.388, p < 0.0001$; 6 dpf: $t(28) = 5.13, p < 0.0001$; 7 dpf: $t(28) = 9.71, p < 0.0001$]. No significant treatment effects on responsiveness to the startle-inducing stimulus during the prepulse or pulse steps were observed at any developmental stage.

3.5.2. Dopaminergic modulation

Dopaminergic modulation is another key mechanism influencing sensorimotor gating and PPI regulation. In mammals, dopaminergic hyperactivity through stimulation of D₂ receptors consistently disrupts PPI, an effect that can be reversed by antipsychotic drugs with D₂ receptor antagonistic properties such as haloperidol (Geyer et al., 2001; Swerdlow et al., 2008). Comparable effects have been reported in zebrafish, supporting the conservation of dopaminergic control of startle modulation within vertebrates (Burgess and Granato, 2007). To further characterize this pathway in early zebrafish development, we assessed whether acute exposure to the dopamine receptor agonist apomorphine alters PPI in 5–7 dpf zebrafish larvae, and whether co-exposure to haloperidol can prevent or reverse these effects. Individual response frequencies and calculated PPI percentage values for each developmental stage are provided in [Supplementary Datasets 7–8](#).

As shown in [Fig. 7B](#), apomorphine exposure resulted in a significant decrease in PPI percentage across all developmental stages compared with controls, using both 50-ms [5 dpf: $U(N_{\text{control}} = 30, N_{\text{apomorphine}} = 30) = 178.0, z = -4.033, p < 0.0001$; 6 dpf: $U(N_{\text{control}} = 35, N_{\text{apomorphine}} = 35) = 258.0, z = -4.174, p < 0.0001$; 7 dpf: $U(N_{\text{control}} = 25, N_{\text{apomorphine}} = 25) = 174.5, z = -2.680, p = 0.007$] and 500-ms [5 dpf: $t(58) = 4.32, p < 0.0001$; 6 dpf: $t(68) = 3.64, p = 0.0005$; 7 dpf: $t(48) = 4.46, p < 0.0001$] prepulse–pulse intervals.

The reversal of PPI impairments elicited by dopaminergic stimulation with apomorphine serves as a validated paradigm for evaluating antipsychotic activity (Burgess and Granato, 2007). Therefore, the effect of a 20-minute pre-treatment with 0.5 μM haloperidol followed by co-exposure for 30 min with 35 μM apomorphine was determined.

As shown in [Fig. 7B](#), in 5–6 dpf zebrafish, haloperidol was unable to reverse the PPI impairment induced by apomorphine. In 7 dpf larvae, however, this D₂ antagonist fully reversed the effect of apomorphine on PPI when a 500-ms interval was used.

3.6. Robustness and validity of Zebra_K⁺ platform

The performance of the automated platform was evaluated by comparing manual and automated analyses of startle kinematics. As shown in [Supplementary Table S1](#), both approaches produced highly consistent results, confirming that the software accurately reproduces manually derived parameters for latency, C-bend angle, and C-bend duration. Similar correspondence between manual and automated quantification of zebrafish startle responses has been previously

Fig. 6. Sensitivity and short-term habituation of the acoustic startle response (ASR) in zebrafish embryos (5 dpf) and early larvae (6–7 dpf) following exposure to ketamine (50 μ M and 500 μ M). ASR frequencies are shown for the sensitivity phase (moderate stimulus: 1000 Hz, 100 μ s, 85.9 dB re 20 μ Pa; ISI = 120 s) and for the early (stimuli 1–5), middle (stimuli 6–10), and late (stimuli 11–15) phases of habituation (startle-inducing stimulus: 1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μ Pa; ISI = 2 s). For each developmental stage, sample sizes were 27 larvae for the control group, 21 larvae for the 50 μ M ketamine group, and 27 larvae for the 500 μ M ketamine group, yielding a total of 15 ASR-percentage values per condition and phase. Data are presented as boxplots in which the box shows the 25th–75th percentiles, the line marks the median, and whiskers represent the minimum and maximum values, showing all data. Kruskal–Wallis test with Bonferroni correction: ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$. All individual ASR-percentage values are provided in [Supplementary Dataset 4](#).

(caption on next page)

Fig. 7. Pharmacological modulation of prepulse inhibition (PPI) of the acoustic startle response (ASR) in zebrafish embryos (5 dpf) and early larvae (6–7 dpf). (A) Effects of 30-min exposure to 50 μM ketamine on PPI. The prepulse consisted of a weak acoustic stimulus (1000 Hz, 20 μs , 74.8 dB re 20 μPa) and the pulse was a startle-inducing stimulus (1000 Hz, 4 ms, 93.7 dB re 20 μPa). The 15 PPI-percentage values obtained at each developmental stage were derived from 36 to 38 embryos (5 dpf), 34–38 larvae (6 dpf), and 36–38 larvae (7 dpf) in the control and ketamine group. (B, left) Effects of 30-min exposure to 35 μM apomorphine on PPI. The 30, 20, and 25 PPI-percentage values obtained at 5, 6, and 7 dpf, respectively, were derived from 30 vs. 39 embryos (5 dpf), 34 vs. 38 larvae (6 dpf), and 31 vs. 33 larvae (7 dpf) in the control and apomorphine groups. (B, right) Rescue of apomorphine-induced PPI impairment by haloperidol (20-min pre-treatment with 0.5 μM haloperidol followed by co-exposure with 35 μM apomorphine). At 5 dpf, the 20 PPI-percentage values were obtained from 16, 23, and 24 embryos in the control, apomorphine, and apomorphine+haloperidol groups, respectively. At 6 and 7 dpf, the 15 PPI-percentage values per stage were obtained from 24, 24, and 26 larvae in the same treatment groups. Data are shown as boxplots where the box represents the 25th–75th percentiles, the line indicates the median, and whiskers show minimum and maximum values, showing all data. Statistical tests: *t*-test or Mann–Whitney *U* test, as appropriate. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. All individual PPI-percentage values are available in [Supplementary Datasets 6–8](#).

reported (Burgess and Granato, 2007).

The robustness of the platform was examined in 5 dpf embryos using Kruskal–Wallis (KW) tests across independent experimental batches and among individual organisms (see [Supplementary Tables S2 and S3](#)). For kinematic parameters, no significant batch effects were detected for latency ($p = 0.122$), maximal angular velocity ($p = 0.072$), C-bend duration ($p = 0.188$), and angle ($p = 0.948$) among experiments. Habituation metrics were largely stable among batches, except for sensitivity ($p = 0.0014$), while prehabituation and the three habituation phases were consistent ($p = 0.162$ – 0.995). In the PPI domain, prepulse, pulse, and PPI 50-ms responses were stable ($p = 0.055$ – 0.766), whereas PPI 500-ms showed a modest batch effect ($p = 0.0105$). No significant inter-individual variability in the kinematic parameters was observed within experiments ([Supplementary Table S3](#)), reflecting normal biological diversity rather than technical inconsistency. Altogether, these analyses indicate that Zebra_K⁺ provides reproducible measurements across experiments and individuals, with only minor differences limited to specific parameters.

In embryos and larvae, the construct and predictive validity of Zebra_K⁺ are supported by its ability to capture the acoustic startle response, habituation, and PPI patterns consistent with those described in zebrafish larvae and other vertebrate models. The developmental progression of these behaviors parallels the maturation of underlying neural circuits, confirming that the platform accurately captures ontogenetic changes in sensorimotor gating. Moreover, pharmacological modulation of habituation and PPI with NMDA antagonists and D₂ agonists demonstrates that Zebra_K⁺ reliably detects neurobiologically relevant effects at early developmental stages. Together, these results validate the platform as a sensitive and predictive tool for assessing neurobehavioral function in zebrafish embryos and larvae.

4. Discussion

This study establishes Zebra_K⁺ as a robust, high-resolution behavioral platform capable of quantifying ASR kinematics, short-term habituation, and PPI across zebrafish development. By extending the capabilities of the adult-oriented Zebra_K to 5–7 dpf stages, the platform enables developmental analyses that are rarely performed within a single experimental framework. The ability to measure early sensorimotor plasticity with kinematic precision provides a methodological bridge between embryonic NAM-relevant stages and more traditional larval assays.

A central finding of this work is that 5 dpf zebrafish embryos exhibit mature short-latency C-bend kinematics, with latency values (4–7 ms) and C-bend durations (~9 ms) in close agreement with previous descriptions of Mauthner-mediated escape responses in larvae (Burgess and Granato, 2007; Marsden and Granato, 2015). Developmental comparisons revealed only a modest increase in latency at 7 dpf, likely reflecting a gradual refinement of inhibitory gating within the reticulospinal network or age-dependent changes in sensory processing. The fact that remaining kinematic parameters did not vary throughout early developmental stages underscores that the escape circuitry is already highly stable by 5 dpf, consistent with prior work showing that the Mauthner neuron and its associated interneuronal pathways are

morphologically and functionally mature shortly after hatching (Koyama et al., 2016). Notably, these larval values also closely parallel those recently reported for adult zebrafish using the Zebra_K platform, where C-bend latencies typically fall in the 8–12 ms range and bend durations remain ~10–12 ms (Koyama et al., 2016). The strong concordance between larval and adult kinematic profiles, despite differences in body size, biomechanics, and sensory ecology, highlights the lifelong conservation of the Mauthner-driven escape motor program and demonstrates that Zebra_K⁺ captures the same fundamental biomechanical signature previously characterized in adult fish.

Our results also refine the developmental profile of ASR sensitivity and habituation. Startle sensitivity to the moderate-intensity stimulus used in the sensitivity phase decreased markedly from 5 to 7 dpf, with younger embryos exhibiting significantly higher response rates than older larvae. In contrast, when a strong startle-inducing pulse was used during the prehabituation phase, responsiveness remained uniformly high across all ages. This distinction indicates that developmental differences emerge primarily under near-threshold stimulus conditions, whereas suprathreshold stimuli reliably trigger startle responses regardless of age (Burgess and Granato, 2007)(Marsden and Granato, 2015). This pattern is consistent with classic work showing that early developmental stages display higher responsiveness to weak acoustic inputs due to immature inhibitory gating within the Mauthner circuit (Eaton et al., 1977) and generally higher auditory sensitivity in larval fish (Zeddies and Fay, 2005). Despite these differences in sensitivity, short-term habituation, one of the most conserved forms of non-associative learning, occurred to a similar extent across all ages. This indicates that the cellular and synaptic mechanisms underlying habituation, involving NMDAR-dependent modulation within hindbrain and subpallial circuits (Marsden and Granato, 2015; Nelson et al., 2023), are already established by 5 dpf. These observations are in line with foundational work showing robust habituation by the end of the embryonic period (5 dpf) and during the initial larval period (6–7 dpf) using either high-speed imaging (Marsden and Granato, 2015; Wolman et al., 2011) or centroid-based analyses (Best et al., 2008; Leuthold et al., 2025).

An important methodological contribution of Zebra_K⁺ is its ability to overcome limitations inherent to centroid-based platforms such as DanioVision (Noldus) or the standard ZebraBox configuration (View-Point). These commercial systems offer major advantages, including very high throughput (typically 48–96 wells), straightforward setup, and robust pipelines for locomotor, thigmotaxis, and anxiety-related assays, making them indispensable tools for large-scale behavioral screening. However, when applied to startle paradigms, displacement-based quantification faces well-known constraints. Zebrafish embryos and larvae spend substantial time near well walls due to thigmotaxis (Norton, 2012; Schnörr et al., 2012), and wall-directed escapes often truncate movement, producing minimal centroid displacement. This can lead displacement-based algorithms to misclassify true startles as non-responses, a problem exacerbated in habituation assays with short interstimulus intervals (see [Supplementary Video S1](#)). A preliminary analysis of our dataset indicates that approximately 15 % of genuine startle responses at 5 dpf terminate against the well wall, resulting in negligible centroid displacement despite a clear C-bend (data not

shown). Moreover, centroid-based systems infer startle occurrence primarily from stage 3 of the escape sequence (burst swimming), which is the most variable component of the response in terms of amplitude, tail-beat frequency, and trajectory (Liu and Hale, 2014; Voesenek et al., 2019). In contrast, Zebra_K* extracts latency and early angular velocity from high-speed video during the first 100 ms post-stimulus, focusing on the highly stereotyped C-bend and counterbend phases. This approach reliably detects short-latency C-bends (SLCs)—the subclass that robustly habituates—while excluding long-latency C-bends (LLCs), which do not consistently habituate and add noise when pooled (Burgess and Granato, 2007; Marsden and Granato, 2015; Wolman et al., 2011). These features reduce false negatives, isolate the response subtype encoding habituation, and increase sensitivity to pharmacological and developmental effects. Importantly, these advantages do not replace the strengths of centroid-based systems, which remain unmatched for high-throughput locomotor and anxiety paradigms, but instead complement them by enabling high-content kinematic analysis optimized for ASR, habituation, and PPI.

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Pharmacological experiments further validated Zebra_K* as a sensitive platform for detecting NMDA- and dopamine-dependent modulation of ASR plasticity. Ketamine consistently reduced habituation and elevated startle sensitivity across all stages, corroborating earlier reports in 5 dpf embryos (Wolman et al., 2011) and adults (Stevanović et al., 2025) and aligning with cellular evidence showing that NMDAR blockade reduces Ca²⁺ signals in the lateral dendrite of the Mauthner neuron, thereby impairing short-term habituation (Marsden and Granato, 2015). Because ketamine altered behavior similarly in 5, 6, and 7 dpf animals, our findings confirm that NMDAR-dependent mechanisms are functional by 5 dpf and can be robustly interrogated within NAM-compatible developmental stages.

Dopaminergic modulation exhibited a more complex developmental profile. Apomorphine reduced PPI at all stages, consistent with conserved D₂-dependent disruption of sensorimotor gating across vertebrates (Geyer et al., 2001; Swerdlow et al., 2008). However, the magnitude of impairment varied: effects were clear at 5 dpf, less pronounced at 6 dpf, and strongest at 7 dpf. These differences likely reflect ongoing maturation of dopaminergic pathways, including the progressive integration of hypothalamic dopaminergic neurons and their projections to hindbrain sensorimotor centers (Tay et al., 2011). The full rescue of apomorphine-induced PPI deficits by haloperidol at 7 dpf mirrors the classical antipsychotic reversal observed in mammals and in 6 dpf zebrafish larvae (Burgess and Granato, 2007), further supporting the developmental emergence of functional D₂-mediated modulation. Importantly, haloperidol was used solely as a pharmacological antagonist, at concentrations previously shown not to affect PPI when administered alone, in accordance with ethical principles and the 3Rs.

Altogether, the present work establishes Zebra_K* as a robust, developmentally versatile, and pharmacologically sensitive platform for analyzing ASR kinematics and plasticity in zebrafish. The platform's ability to generate high-resolution behavioral readouts in both embryos and larvae maximizes compatibility with non-animal testing directives while enabling targeted investigation of distinct neuromodulatory pathways across development. These capabilities create a framework for selecting the most appropriate developmental stage for specific mechanistic or toxicological endpoints—for example, leveraging 5 dpf embryos for NMDA-mediated habituation studies and 7 dpf larvae for dopaminergic modulation of PPI.

By integrating precise kinematic analysis, developmental profiling, and pharmacological validation, Zebra_K* provides a powerful methodological advance for neurobehavioral research. Its application will facilitate more accurate characterization of sensorimotor circuits, enable high-content neurotoxicological screening, and promote the adoption of refined NAM-aligned approaches in zebrafish neuroscience.

5. Conclusions

This study presents Zebra_K*, a modular, high-throughput platform for the automated kinematic analysis of the acoustic startle response (ASR) in zebrafish. Building on the original Zebra_K system for adults, the new module extends these capabilities to 5 dpf embryos and 6–7 dpf larvae, enabling continuous assessment of ASR kinematics, sensitivity, and neuroplasticity throughout zebrafish development. To our knowledge, Zebra_K* is the first unified platform that allows seamless analysis from embryonic to adult stages simply by changing the experimental module.

Our findings demonstrate that 5 dpf zebrafish already exhibit mature ASR kinematics and display both habituation and prepulse inhibition. Across development, NMDA receptor-dependent modulation was consistently observed from 5 to 7 dpf. Dopaminergic modulation was also present at early stages, as apomorphine reduced PPI at 5 dpf, although its effects varied across development: modulation was weaker at 6 dpf and more pronounced at 7 dpf, where haloperidol partially rescued the apomorphine-induced deficit. These differences likely reflect gradual maturation of the circuits underlying sensorimotor gating rather than the de novo emergence of dopaminergic influence at a specific age. Overall, Zebra_K* enables detailed characterization of ASR plasticity and its pharmacological modulation in early zebrafish development, providing a robust framework for mechanistic, neurobehavioral, and neurotoxicological applications.

These results underscore that developmental stage selection is important when probing specific neuropharmacological mechanisms. While NMDA receptor-dependent modulation was robust among all stages examined, dopaminergic modulation showed age-dependent variation in magnitude. Thus, Zebra_K* not only serves as a versatile research tool but also provides a practical framework for aligning developmental stage choice with the neurobiological question of interest—for example, leveraging 5 dpf embryos for NAMs-oriented neuroplasticity studies and 7 dpf larvae when investigating more mature dopaminergic contributions to sensorimotor gating. Together, these features position Zebra_K* as a reliable and scalable platform for developmental neurobehavioral research and neurotoxicological screening.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ouwais Aljabasini: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Niki Tagkalidou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Demetrio Raldúa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Eva Prats:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Sergi Pujol:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology. **Carlos Barata:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Josep Maria Porta:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the clarity and readability of the manuscript. The tool was employed exclusively for language refinement and rephrasing, not for content generation. All content was subsequently reviewed and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Demetrio reports financial support was provided by Spanish Ministry Research and Innovation. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.neuro.2025.103372](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2025.103372).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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